

PERCEPTION OF BARRIERS TO SUCCESSION PLANNING IN FAMILY- OWNED CONSTRUCTION FIRMS IN GHANA

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Abstract: Purpose – This paper examines the barriers to undertaking succession planning in family-owned construction firms. This would unearth the reasons why family-owned construction firms are unable to undertake succession planning which is identified as the leading panacea to unsurvivability of family-owned construction firms beyond the owner-manager.

Design/methodology/approach – The research explored these barriers to undertaking succession planning in family-owned construction firms using a survey approach within a cross-sectional design to collect data from 142 owner-managers of family-owned construction firms in Ghana. Data obtained were subjected to descriptive statistics and subsequently, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and other non-parametric tests were used to examine the differences in the identification of the barriers.

Findings – The study established external barriers, incumbent-related barriers, incumbent-management-related barriers, management successor-related barriers, and successor-related barriers as the most crucial barriers preventing the implementation of succession planning in family-owned construction firms in Ghana. Findings from the study ranked incumbent-related barriers as the most significant barrier preventing the implementation of succession planning and family-related barriers as the least important. The extracted barriers have satisfactory values for KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity according to the results and this makes the findings fit for further analytical tests on succession planning.

Limitations/implications – The study recommends a future study into the perceptions of successors towards succession planning because the perceptions of incumbents and successors may differ significantly and a willing successor is a recipe for effective succession planning.

Practical implications –The findings are important for practice because successions are initiated, controlled, and driven by the owner-managers. Understanding the perception of owner-managers towards succession planning enables policymakers and the government to design initiatives to encourage and help shape the perceptions of owner-managers towards succession planning.

Originality/value –Investigating the theoretical and practical problems preventing the implementation of succession planning in family-owned construction firms is crucial because family-owned Construction firms are collapsing rapidly after the death of the owner-manager due largely to a lack of succession planning.

Keywords: Family firm, family-owned construction firm, barriers, succession, and succession planning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Family firms constitute the earliest form of business organization in the world with stimulating effects on social and economic development (Guo et al., 2019). They are also among the most common firms globally (Nordqvist et al., 2013). Thompson (2021) describes family-owned businesses as the heart and soul of the economy and civil society. It is axiomatic that family-owned construction firms are the most dominant firms in the construction industry (Anzagira et al., 2021). Eyiah & Cook (2003) suggest that in Ghana, almost all indigenous construction firms operate as family firms. Family-owned construction firms have significant importance to economic growth (Anzagira et al., 2022). For instance, the construction sector's contribution to GDP in recent years is more than 15% (International Trade Association, 2022). They are also crucial to the country's plan for transformation and development (Bowen et al., 2007) due to the economic projects these firms embark on which are widely dispersed geographically (Toor & Ofori, 2008). They also play a vital role in job creation, raising the standard of living, and contributing to growth in their areas of intervention (Saan et al., 2018). According to Arthur-Aidoo et al. (2018), a nation's desire to develop and meet the infrastructure needs of the economy is hinged on the growth of Family-owned construction firms. However, instead of growth, there is a high failure or demise of construction firms (including family-owned construction firms) (Holt, 2013; Tserng et al., 2011), which has attracted the attention of researchers in current studies (Holt, 2013). The failure of these family-owned construction firms also has dire consequences not only for the family, the business, and their employees but also for the health of the economy (Miller et al., 2003). The failure of the firms usually associated with the death of the founder has been blamed principally on a lack of succession planning (Ogundele et al., 2012).

According to Lušňáková et al. (2019), the problem of succession is a test every family firm must pass otherwise the founder's efforts remain wasted. Several authors have underscored the significance succession planning plays in the growth and continued sustainability of the firm (LeCounte, 2020; Akinniyi et al., 2020) and in enhancing family harmony (Porfirio et al., 2019; Gilding et al., 2015). Succession planning results in a seamless leadership transition (Adewale et al., 2011), making firms successful and more profitable in the long term (Behn et al., 2005; Lee et al., 2003; Sharma et al., 2003b). This also ensures the business's viability, upholds the family's moral character, and meets the interests of any family members involved in the process (Cabrera-suárez & Martín-santana, 2012). The satisfaction of the diverse stakeholders in the company is further elevated (Venter et al., 2005; Cabrera-Saurez et al., 2001). Succession planning is also significant to fill leadership positions (King, 2013; Mehrabani & Mohamad, 2011; Allen, 2005), developing individuals to increase their managerial authority, and conserve corporate memory and crucial skills (Mehrabani & Mohamad, 2011). It reduces the time and expense associated with hiring and selecting external staff (Adebola, 2019) whilst ensuring the firm's long-term viability and sustainability (Mandl, 2008). Researchers question why more firms are not implementing succession planning despite its numerous benefits (Kowalewski et al., 2011), and the fact that the lack of succession planning is a leading cause of family firm mortality (Villegas et al., 2019). Scholars further suggest that in the global economy, succession planning is a huge challenge for business survival and continuity (Tabor & Vadarman, 2020; Alayo et al., 2016), including family-owned construction firms.

According to Helsen et al. (2017), succession involves the transfer of both ownership and the control of the firm from one generation to the next. Some researchers view the succession process as a mutual behavior involving critical players in the firm and other stakeholders of the firm, where coordination between the actors is necessary (Kandade et al., 2020). Other scholars also view succession as a process that provides an opportunity for firms to grow in a rapidly changing environment (Xavier et al., 2021; Dyck et al., 2002; Cabrera-Saurez et al., 2001). Garman & Glawe (2004) suggest that succession planning is a structured process involving the identification and preparation of a potential successor to assume a new position. According to Rothwell (2001), it must be a deliberate and systematic effort to ensure that key positions are filled with a policy to retain and develop employees' knowledge and skills for the future and encourage individual advancement. In the family business context, succession planning is the means by which ownership and managerial control are transmitted from one family member to another (Aladejebi, 2021; Chrisman et al., 2003). Bayer (2020) suggests that succession planning for construction firms entails understanding the particular challenges the company is facing and developing a strategy to address them. In the construction industry, most firms don't plan for succession (Taylor & McGraw, 2004). The primary goal of undertaking succession planning is to achieve a sustainable transfer of ownership, control, and responsibility within the family business for the following generation (Ramadani et al., 2017; Kaneff, 2011). Duh et al. (2007) refer to succession as the planned and formal process that makes it possible for one

generation to successfully transfer ownership and managerial control to the next. Succession planning also increases the likelihood of a successful succession (Sharma et al., 2001), and that the firm owner wishes to hand over the business to a family member (Abdullah et al., 2011). Succession planning involves the process of transferring managerial control from the owner-manager to the next generation of family members (Nnabuiife & Okoli, 2017; Ukaegbu, 2003). Other researchers diagnose succession planning as the process of transferring both ownership and the control of the business between generations within the same family (LeCounte, 2020; Helsen et al., 2017).

Past researchers have outlined the numerous benefits of succession planning as discussed above. It is also the contention that the success of a family firm is not measured by profit or revenue per se, but is judged by the number of generations of the family that has successfully gone through the succession process. However, there is a mirage of bottlenecks and barriers militating against undertaking succession planning in family-owned construction firms. These barriers according to Mehrabani & Mohamad (2011) are varied and can be found in the organizational culture, strategy, and economic conditions among others. Researchers posit that owner-managers lack of knowledge and ignorance of what succession planning entails negatively impacts succession planning (Obadan & Ohiorenoya, 2013; Onuoha, 2012; Duh et al., 2007). This makes a majority of them either ignore or circumvent succession planning practices (Dana, 2019; Dana & Smyrnios, 2010; Smyrnios & Dana, 2007). It is also the reason why despite the conclusion of Miller & Le Breton-miller (2006) that long-term strategic planning is the constant common factor among well-performing family businesses, a sizable portion of family businesses have not prioritized succession planning. Ignorance of the owner-manager of the succession planning process inhibits the process for some owner-managers (Obadan & Ohiorenoya, 2013), and for others, a lack of it (Phikiso & Tengeh, 2017; Hjorth, 2016; Visser & Chiloane-Tsoka, 2014; Onuoha, 2013; Ogundele et al., 2012; Farrington et al., 2012). This culminates in the failure of family firms to transition into the next generation. Marshall and others in their 2006 study of 205 family businesses confirmed that there was a significant positive relationship between knowing the importance of succession planning and having formal succession plans for family businesses (Marshall et al., 2006). Additionally, the lack of knowledge of succession planning makes the founder have strong psychological deterrents to undertaking succession planning, particularly his aversion to dealing with his mortality; his resistance to the idea of relinquishing control over the company; his fear of losing his identity; and his rivalry and jealousy towards prospective successors (Lansberg, 1988). Owner-managers also avoid the topic of succession planning whenever a conversation about it emerges with some sort of hostility as if the discussion of the topic relates directly to their demise (Oyeladun, 2020; Sharma et al., 2001). According to Ogundele et al. (2012) and Kets de Vries (1993), most business owners never consider the need to prepare a suitable successor in the event of their exit because doing so would require acknowledging one's mortality and making plans for death, which goes against the cultural values and beliefs of the society. This may also be because a majority of incumbents are still strong and healthy hence reluctant to retire from active participation in the day-to-day operations of their enterprises; not knowing what a succession plan is; no capable hand to hand over the business to and fear of mismanagement; the feeling by the entrepreneurs themselves that they are still strong and healthy; the fact that their children or relations are not interested in the business; and that majority of the firms are not incorporated (Onuoha, 2013b). This is supported by a 2003 study by Allen & Langowitz that found 13.4% of family business members believe their CEO will "never" retire (Allen & Langowitz, 2003). Researchers (Perrenoud & Sullivan, 2016; Ibrahim & Ellis, 2003) suggest that in addition to the emotional attachment to the business, fear of retirement and a lack of hobbies and interests outside of work may also play a role in the unwillingness to plan. Past studies have also shown that the difficulty in choosing the successor and the selection process during succession planning makes the succession process to fail (Xavier et al., 2021; De Massis et al., 2016). For instance, the selection of an unmotivated and less interested successor would stagnate the succession process in family firms (Dana, 2019; De Massis et al., 2008; Ward, 2004). This may also be problematic for the other siblings which may result in the departure of such children from the firm for such a reason (Ogundele et al., 2012; Ortiz, 2007). Additionally, De Massis et al. (2008) posits that a lack of trust in the potential successor and lack of commitment from the potential successor challenges the succession process. Lack of a qualified and well-prepared successor to take over the reins of authority limits a successful transition into the next generation (Dana, 2019; Ward, 2004). This is also because inadequate grooming of the successors may result in young employees experiencing distressing uncertainty and detachment towards leadership roles (Shamsuddin et al., 2012). According to scholars, the relationship between the owner-manager and the successor plays a crucial role in the succession process (Venter et al., 2006; Venter et al., 2005; Brockhaus, 2004; Dickinson, 2000; Chrisman et al., 1998), and the timing and effectiveness of the process (Brockhaus, 2004). It also has an important effect on the preparation process of the successor

(Venter et al., 2005). Conflicts between incumbents and potential successors serves to inhibit the succession process (De Massis et al., 2008; Davis & Harveston, 1998; Lansberg, 1988). According to De Massis et al. (2008), conflicts between the successor and non-family employees, a lack of confidence in the successor, and a lack of commitment by the successor are three factors that could lead to a bad relationship. In addition, Ambrose (1983) identified sibling rivalry and disparate expectations as important barriers to undertaking succession planning. Fulmer (2002) posits that even without intra-family conflicts, a lack of support from senior management during succession planning will result in a failed or ineffective transition. Researchers (Al Suwaidi et al., 2020; Gothard & Austin, 2013) suggest that without the support of all employees in the firm, especially the firm's leaders, succession planning would be a mirage. The Nation's laws about business and succession in terms of the Companies Act of Ghana (Act 992) which determines how shares may be transferred, the Matrimonial Causes Act (Act 367) and the Intestate Succession law (Act 111) which determines how the estate of a deceased may be dealt with also serves as stumbling blocks to succession planning. In addition, the cultural and inheritance issues and plans in the country pertaining to the distribution of a man's estate also serves to inhibit the succession planning process (e.g. Aderonke, 2014; Musa & Semasinghe, 2014; Onuoha, 2013; Ogundele et al., 2012; Duh et al., 2007; Maphosa, 1999; Bernes & Hershan, 1976). In Ghana, the dominant systems of inheritance are the patrilineal and matrilineal systems and these determines who inherits from who. Again the extended family system and the polygamous marriage structure also inhibits the succession planning process.

This study submits that despite the crucial role succession planning plays in the continuity of family firms, family-owned construction firms are collapsing at an outrageously overwhelming rate due to bottlenecks identified by researchers which prevent the planning of succession. This study thus hypothesizes the effects of the various challenges on succession planning and proceeds to look at the research design.

H1: External barriers negatively affect succession planning.

H2: Family-related barriers negatively affect succession planning

H3: Management-Incumbent-related barriers negatively affect succession planning

H4: Incumbent-related barriers negatively affect succession planning

H5: Management-successor-related barriers negatively affect succession planning.

H6: Successor-related barriers negatively affect succession planning

2. RESEARCH DESIGN

This paper examines the perceptions of barriers to succession planning in family-owned construction firms in Ghana. To achieve the aim of the study, a survey method supported by a literature review was employed. Xavier et al. (2021) suggest that good research depends on the selection of sound research techniques that are most suitable to answer the research issues at hand. The use of secondary data from the internet, journals, and articles to support primary data has been widely accepted (Kowo et al., 2021). Questionnaire administration within a cross-sectional design was used to obtain responses from family-owned construction firms in Ghana. According to Oppenheim (2003), questionnaires designed to solicit responses for primary data must be easy to understand, concise, clear, able to be answered in an unbiased way, and easy to analyze to address the research goal. Purposive and snowball sampling was employed to solicit responses from owner-managers of family-owned construction firms in Ghana. This is because there is no comprehensive list of contractors in Ghana and most importantly, family-owned construction firms (Anzagira et al., 2021). Therefore, to maximize the level of participation, participating firms contacted had either their name associated with the name of a person or by recommendation from other contractors where the shareholding structure of the firm i.e. ownership and management were known to be vested in a family.

Data Collection

Owner-managers of family-owned construction firms constituted the unit of analysis in this study. The study concentrated on the perspective of owner-managers on the barriers to undertaking succession planning in family-owned construction firms in Ghana. A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed based on these sampling criteria and 142 usable

questionnaires were retrieved representing a 71% response rate. Ethical considerations were taken seriously at all times beginning with assurance in the questionnaire to the respondents of the confidentiality of their responses.

The survey results indicated that the majority of the respondents were males (78.2%), while 21.8% were females. Most of the firms were also relatively young with 81.7% of the respondents indicating their firms were below 20 years whilst 18.3% had firms that were over 20 years old. In terms of the size of the firm, the results indicated that 38% of respondents indicated that their firms employ 1-9 persons, 26.8% have 10-29 employees, 21.8% have 30-40 employees whilst 13.4% employ over 40 workers.

The research instrument

The research instrument was adapted to answer the research questions and fulfill the objectives of the research. The questionnaire consisted of multichotomous questions on a 7-point Likert scale showing their level of agreement to be ranked from 1 to 7 where 1 shows strongly disagree and 7 shows strongly agree, to the perceptions of barriers to undertaking succession planning in family-owned construction firms. These consisted of barriers obtained from and emphasized in the literature review. It is thus interesting to get the perceptions of youthful entrepreneurs who are yet to undertake succession planning amidst those who are undertaking the process.

Data analysis

The collated data were analyzed utilizing selected descriptive statistical methods at the significance level of 0.05. The first analysis was to rank the critical barriers based on their mean score; the second was to perform the one-sample t-test to check if there was variation in the agreement ratings of the barriers among the sex of respondents and the ages of respondents; the third was to explore the underlying relationships among the critical barriers through the Principal Component Factor Analysis (PCFA). To ensure the statistical validity and reliability of the constructs, the questionnaire was pre-tested by a pilot using five respondents made up of three owner-managers and two researchers from academia. The responses from the pilot survey were used to refine the questionnaire.

3. RESULTS

Validity and reliability testing

The study employed the scales developed by Sharma et al. (2003a) to test the internal consistency and reliability of the study using Cronbach's alpha. It confirmed that the scales were reliable with Cronbach's alpha values of 0.915 (i.e. above 0.70). The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure was used to verify the sampling adequacy for using factor analysis. The results provided a KMO value of 0.767 (above the threshold of 0.6) according to Hair Jr. et al. (2010), and the Bartlett's test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 (171) = 1013.932, p \leq 0.001$) and hence provides support for factorization of variables (Hair et al., 2014). Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted using the principal component and varimax with Kaiser Normalization. The communality extraction value of a potentially significant variable must produce an extraction eigenvalue greater than 0.50 at initial extraction to achieve the reliability and interpretation of the factor analysis result. Twelve variables were excluded from the thirty-one variables used as the combined effect of their communalities and cross-loadings from the rotation matrix was below 0.50. The remaining indicators were satisfactory with communalities and other measures. A meticulous consideration of the variables was undertaken to summarize the barriers to succession planning according to the components and to identify the likely interrelation among the indicators confined in each component and the outer loadings. Based on the rotated component matrix and the total variance explained, a six-factor model in line with the study hypotheses explaining 67.6% of variance was retained and aligned to the original factor structure.

Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive statistics and correlation coefficients are displayed in Table 1 where, on average, above mid-point mean scores were observed across factors where the highest scores were on BIR ($M = 9.597, SD = 0.052$) and the lowest was on BFR ($M = 1.215, SD = 0.059$). Several positive and significant correlations between the factors were observed, which highlights relatively high levels of associations between these factors and succession planning, and vice versa.

Table 1: Discriminant Validity of constructs (Fornell-Larcker Criterion) – Barriers of Succession Planning for FOCFs Model

	Mean	Sd	BEBC	BFR	BIMR	BIR	BMSR	BSR
External Barriers	5.940	0.038	0.871					
Family-related	1.215	0.059	0.177	0.786				
Incumbent-Management	3.343	0.039	0.192	0.426	1.000			
Incumbent related	9.597	0.052	0.330	0.147	0.071	0.730		
Management-Successor	4.131	0.047	0.107	0.502	0.200	0.169	0.902	
Successor related	3.575	0.049	0.257	0.220	0.192	0.576	0.303	0.787

Hypothesis testing

Based on the proposition of the study, a gradual analysis of the structural model was used to test the hypothesis (i.e. provide a detailed picture of the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables). According to Aibinu & Al-lawati (2010), a high path coefficient indicates a stronger influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The model summary in Table 2 indicates an adjusted R² of 0.725, which means that this model explains 72.5% variance in the dependent variable (succession planning). For each of the study hypotheses, coefficients were calculated separately as per each hypothesis and are interpreted as follows. Table 2 shows a negative significant relationship between External barriers ($\beta=-0.224$, t-value=5.940, p-value= 0.000) and succession planning which provides support for H1. However, for Family related barriers and succession planning, a non-significant negative relationship is observed ($\beta=-0.072$, t-value=1.215, p-value= 0.224), which does not provide support for H2. In terms of Incumbent Management and succession planning, a negative significant relationship with succession planning is observed ($\beta=-0.132$, t-value=3.343, p-value= 0.001), which provides support for H3. For Incumbent related barriers and succession planning, a negative significant relationship is observed ($\beta=-0.503$, t-value=9.597, p-value= 0.000) and this provides support for H4. Management successor-related barriers and succession planning yielded a negative significant relationship ($\beta=-0.194$, t-value=4.131, p-value= 0.000), supporting hypothesis H5. Lastly, a negative and significant relationship between Successor-related barriers and Succession planning is observed ($\beta=-0.175$, t-value=3.575, p-value= 0.000), which provides support for H6.

Table 2: Path Coefficients of Barriers to Succession Planning model

	R Square	R Square Adjusted	Q ²	Q ² _predict	
Succession Planning	0.736	0.725	0.375	0.713	
Path direction	Coefficient β	Sample Coeff.	Std. Dev.	t-value	p-value
External Barriers -> Succession Planning	-0.224	-0.223	0.038	5.940	0.000
Family-related -> Succession Planning	-0.072	-0.076	0.059	1.215	0.224
Incumbent Management -> Succession Planning	-0.132	-0.130	0.039	3.343	0.001
Incumbent related -> Succession Planning	-0.503	-0.504	0.052	9.597	0.000
Management Successor -> Succession Planning	-0.194	-0.192	0.047	4.131	0.000
Successor related -> Succession Planning	-0.175	-0.177	0.049	3.575	0.000

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

An initial subjection of all barriers to a one-way ANOVA analysis evidenced that all the barriers had mean scores above 3.0 implying that respondents considered them as challenges hampering undertaking succession planning in FOCFs in Ghana though not at the same level of criticality. This enabled further analysis to be undertaken including factor analysis which then grouped barriers into components for further analysis and interpretation of their criticality levels. Statistical support for the study hypotheses highlights the importance of external barriers, incumbent management-related barriers, incumbent-related barriers, management successor-related barriers, and successor-related barriers in preventing the implementation of a succession planning programme in family-owned construction firms. External barriers from the study emerge as negative and significant and the second most critical barrier to undertaking succession planning (H1).

However, it is surprising that Family-related barriers were negative but not significant (H2). A plausible explanation may be that similar to prior studies, a harmonious family environment greatly contributes to business sustainability and profitability (Bizri, 2016). Besides, most family-related issues are heralded by either the incumbent or the successor and turn to be absorbed by those categories of problems. Incumbent-management-related barriers emerge as negative and significant bottlenecks to succession planning (H3) because the duo issues of the incumbent and management could bring the family firm to a halt. This is not surprising as it is observed that sometimes the management of the firm are themselves obstacles to planning for leadership transitions (Perrenoud & Sullivan, 2013). It is suggested that a lack of senior-level support during the transition will make succession planning either ineffective or fail (Fulmer, 2002). Incumbent-related barriers emerge from the study as the most critical group of barriers hindering the implementation of succession planning (H4). This group of barriers having been identified as the most significant is not surprising given the critical role that the owner-manager plays in initiating, controlling, directing, and managing the succession planning process (Anzagira et al., 2022). This is also consistent with the findings of several scholars who have concluded that the succession planning process is crucially dependent on the owner-manager (Oyeladun, 2020; Cho et al., 2018; Zellweger et al., 2011; Miller et al., 2003) since they play a vital role in the succession process (Daspit et al., 2016; Marshall et al., 2006). Management-successor-related barriers have also been identified to have a significant negative effect on succession planning (H5). The relationship between the successor and the staff (including management) can either make or unmake the success of a succession planning programme. It further emerged that Successor-related barriers were negatively significant barriers to succession planning. This is concerned with a lack of the requisite skills (De Massis et al., 2008; Kenyon-Rouvinez & Ward, 2005), unpreparedness to take over the reins of authority (Dana, 2019; Ward, 2004), and lack of commitment (De Massis et al., 2008; Porfirio et al., 2019) by the potential successor.

5. CONCLUSION, CONTRIBUTION, AND LIMITATION

This study contributes to family business literature and construction management literature by examining the effects of barriers on the implementation of succession planning in family-owned construction firms. The consequence of this study's findings is the empirical evidence and understanding of the significant roadblocks to undertaking succession planning. It is trite that identification or knowledge of the problem constitutes the foremost significant step to solving or eliminating it by planning against it and thus ensuring widespread undertaking of succession planning in family-owned construction firms in Ghana. It would enable owner-managers of family-owned construction firms to devise strategies and measures to eliminate these obstacles. Other contractors and consultants within the construction sub-sector with succession planning intentions would find these revelations useful to be able to fashion out measures to eradicate these barriers. Other stakeholders (including policymakers and researchers) interested in promoting succession planning within family-owned construction firms because of their significance in the economic development space of the country would also be able to devise policy initiatives targeting the elimination of bottlenecks against succession planning in family-owned construction firms in Ghana.

This paper also presented only a part of the PhD research which sought to identify the barriers to undertaking succession planning in family-owned construction firms in Ghana. Based on a questionnaire survey conducted on a sample of 142 family-owned construction firms, interesting facts can be stated about succession issues in this category of firms.

Novelty: Family-owned construction firms get extinct with the death of the founder due largely to a lack of succession planning. The empirical evidence that the research offers would guide policymakers and academics to identify the most critical roadblocks and assign resources efficiently to overcome these challenges.

Practical implications: This study seeks to exhume the challenges to succession planning such that contractors would be mindful of them and ensure that they easily undertake succession planning to ensure survival and continuity.

Areas of future research: The study recommends that researchers in the future delve into what drives the implementation of a successful succession process to invigorate the efforts of the contractors whilst diminishing the effects of the roadblocks identified.

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Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The author(s) declare no potential conflicts of interest concerning the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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